

Deploying End to End Website on AWS

Abstract— Cyber security and secure software deployment are issues that cut across multiple sectors— aerospace, defence, energy, critical infrastructure, industrial automation, medical devices, telecommunications, and more. What these disparate sectors have in common is that a malicious, network-borne intrusion can cause untold damage, whether financial or physical, and even threaten human safety. Fortunately, there are security-strengthening techniques and solutions for cyber security research that can apply in all of these areas.

Amazon Web Services offers multiple options for provisioning your IT infrastructure and the deployment of your applications. Whether it is a simple three-tier application or a complex set of workloads, the deployment model varies from customer to customer. But with the right techniques, AWS can help you pick the best strategy and tool set for deploying an infrastructure that can handle your workload.

CLOUD DEPLOYMENT MODEL

The integration of software-as-a-service (SaaS), platform-as-a-service (PaaS), and infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS) into the cloud, to act as a solution that allows users to access data is known as cloud deployment. It works as your virtual computing environment with a choice of deployment model depending on how much data you want to store and who has access to the infrastructure

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Types of Cloud Deployment Model

Most cloud hubs have tens of thousands of servers and storage devices to enable fast loading. It is often possible to choose a geographic area to put the data “closer” to users. Thus, deployment models for cloud computing are categorized based on their location. To know which model would best fit the requirements of your organization.

Public Cloud

The name says it all. It is accessible by the public. Public deployment models in the cloud are perfect for organizations with growing and fluctuating demands. It also makes a great choice for companies with low-security concerns. Thus, you pay a cloud service provider for networking services, compute virtualization & storage available on the public internet.

Fig- Public Cloud

Benefits of Public Cloud

- Minimal Investment
- No Hardware Set-up
- No Infrastructure Management

Private Cloud

Fig-1.1.2 Private Cloud

Now that you understand what the public cloud could offer you, of course, you are keen to know what a private cloud can do. Companies that look for cost efficiency and greater control over data & resources will find the private cloud a more suitable choice. What it means is that it will be integrated with your data center and managed by your IT team. Alternatively, you can also choose to host it externally. When it comes to customization, the private cloud offers bigger opportunities that help meet specific organization's requirements. It's also a wise choice for mission-critical processes that may have frequently changing requirements

Benefits of Private Cloud

- Data Privacy
- Security
- Supports Legacy Systems

Limitations of Private Cloud

- Higher Cost
- Fixed Scalability
- High Maintenance

Community Cloud

The community cloud operates in a way that is similar to the public cloud. There's just one difference – it allows access to only a specific set of users who share common

objectives and use cases. This type of deployment model of cloud computing is managed and hosted internally or by a third-party vendor. The community cloud operates in a way that is similar to the public cloud. There's just one difference - it allows access to only a specific set of users who share common objectives and use cases. This type of deployment model of cloud computing is managed and hosted internally or by a third-party vendor. However, you can also choose a combination of all three.

Fig-1.1.3 Community Cloud

Benefits of Community Cloud

- Smaller Investment
- Setup Benefits

Limitations of Community Cloud

- Shared Resources
- Not as Popular

Hybrid Cloud

As the name suggests, a hybrid cloud is a combination of two or more cloud architectures. While each model in the hybrid cloud functions differently, it is all part of the same architecture. Further, as part of this deployment of the cloud computing model, the internal, or external providers can offer resources. Let's understand the hybrid model better. A company that has critical data will prefer storing on a private cloud, while less sensitive data can be stored on a public cloud. The hybrid cloud is also frequently used for 'cloud bursting'. It means, suppose an organization runs an application on-premises, but due to heavy load, they can burst into the public cloud.

Fig-1.1.4 Hybrid Cloud

Benefits of Hybrid Cloud

- Cost-Effectiveness
- Security
- Flexibility

Limitations and future of project

Limitations of Application:

1. **Costs:** AWS services come with associated costs. Be aware of the pricing model for each service. You use, and monitor your usage to avoid unexpected expenses.
2. **Resource Limits:** Each AWS service has its own resource limitations. Ensure that your application adheres to these limits, such as the number of EC2 instances, storage capacity, or database connections.
3. **Region Availability:** Not all AWS services are available in every region. Check the AWS Regional Services List to ensure that the services you plan to use are available in your desired region.
4. **Security:** Implement security best practices, such as using Virtual Private Clouds (VPCs), configuring security groups, and managing access using Identity and Access Management (IAM).
5. **Scalability:** Plan for scalability from the beginning. Utilize auto-scaling groups to automatically adjust the number of instances based on demand. Consider using Amazon Cloud Front for content delivery and Amazon RDS for managed database scaling.

AMAZON WEB SERVICES

Amazon Web Services (AWS) is the world's most comprehensive and broadly adopted cloud platform, offering over 200 fully featured services from data centers globally. Millions of customers- including the fastest-growing startups, largest enterprises, and leading government agencies- are using AWS to lower costs, become more agile, and innovate faster

Most Functionality

- Largest community of consumers and partners
- Most Secure
- Fastest pace of Innovation

Amazon Relational Database Service (Amazon RDS) is a web service that makes it easier to set up, operate, and scale a relational database in the AWS Cloud. It provides cost-efficient, resizable capacity for an industry-standard relational database and manages common database administration tasks.

Amazon Simple Storage Service (Amazon S3) is an object storage service that offers industry-leading scalability, data availability, security, and performance. Customers of all sizes and industries can use Amazon S3 to store and protect any amount of data for a range of use cases, such as data lakes, websites, mobile applications, backup and restore, archive, enterprise applications, IoT devices, and big data analytics. Amazon S3 provides management features so that you can optimize, organize, and configure access to your data to meet your specific business, organizational, and compliance requirements

Amazon Elastic Compute Cloud (Amazon EC2) provides scalable computing capacity in the Amazon Web Services (AWS) Cloud. Using Amazon EC2 eliminates your need to invest in hardware up front, so you can develop and deploy applications faster. You can use Amazon EC2 to launch as many or as few virtual servers as you need, configure security and networking, and manage storage. Amazon EC2 enables you to scale up or down to handle changes in requirements or

spikes in popularity, reducing your need to forecast traffic.

Amazon Route 53 is a highly available and scalable Domain Name System (DNS) web service. You can use Route 53 to perform three main functions in any combination: domain registration, DNS routing, and health checking.

SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

MODULES

There are five Modules

- Creating the Website
- Setting up the AWS
- Connecting EC2 to our Machine and RDS
- Cloning the Website code into EC2
- Deploying the Website in AWS Cloud

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig.System Architecture

The shows the architectural diagram of this project defines the flow of data for deploying the website on AWS

CREATING THE WEBSITE

Create a Student Database Website using HTML and CSS (frontend) and Python (backend) in Visual Studio. The Website should contain fields such as student_id; first_name; last_name; dob; y gender; email; phone_no; address; department; skills; image.

Fig- Creating the Website.

SETTING UP THE AWS

A DB instance is an isolated database environment running in the cloud. It is the basic building block of Amazon RDS. A DB instance can contain multiple usercreated databases, and can be accessed using the same client tools and applications you might use to access a standalone database instance. DB instances are simple to create and modify with the Amazon AWS command line tools, Amazon RDS API operations, or the AWS Management Console.

- Step-1: In Amazon Management Console, create a database ‘studentinfo’ with engine option as MySQL in the RDS service.

To upload your data (photos, videos, documents, etc.) to Amazon S3, you must first create an S3 bucket in one of the AWS Regions. A bucket is a container for objects stored in Amazon S3. Every object is contained in a bucket. In terms of implementation, buckets and objects are AWS resources, and Amazon S3 provides APIs for you to manage them.

Step-2: Create a bucket ‘addstudentinfo’ in the S3 service.

An instance is a virtual server in the AWS Cloud. With Amazon EC2, you can set up and configure the operating system and applications that run on your instance. When you

sign up for AWS, you can get started with Amazon EC2 using AWS Free Tier.

Step-3: Create a instance i.e., server to deploy as ‘my web server’ with AMI as Ubuntu server in the EC2 service.

A hosted zone is analogous to a traditional DNS zone file; it represents a collection of records that can be managed together, belonging to a single parent domain name. All resource record sets within a hosted zone must have the hosted zone's domain name as a suffix.

Step-4: Create a hosted zone ‘mystudent-database.tk’ in the Route53 service.

Fig- Setting up the AWS

CONNECTING EC2 TO OUR MACHINE AND RDS

Connecting EC2 server to our Machine

- Step-1: In terminal, go to the place where you saved the Key-pair.
- Step-2: The command to connect is “ssh -i ./key-pair name ubuntu@ IP address of EC2”.

Connecting EC2 server to RDS

- Step-1: In Ubuntu server, update the machine “sudo apt-get update” and install mysql-client “sudo apt-get install mysql-client”.
- Step-2: The command to connect is “mysql -h endpoint of database in RDS – username of the database –password of the database”. Now, we are inside MySQL Shell.
- Step-3: Create database ‘studentinfo’ and table ‘student’ using MySQL commands inside the shel with required fields.

CLONING THE WEBSITE CODE INTO EC2

Step-1: Save the code in the local server i.e. terminal and the command is “git commit -m “saved code” ”. At a high level,

GitHub is a website and cloud-based service that helps developers

store and manage their code, as well as track and control changes to their code. A repository contains all of your project's files and each file's revision history. You can discuss and manage your project's work within the repository.

- Step-2: Go to EC2 server again. Clone the code into GitHub. The command is “git clone URL of your repository.git”.

- Step-3: Push the code and the command is “git push origin2 master”

Step-4: Go into your repository inside EC2 server. The command is “cd name of your repository”

- Step-5 : Install

THE WEBSITE

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Student Database" with the following fields and controls:

- Get Student Information (button)
- Student ID: Enter your Student ID (text input)
- First Name: Enter your First Name (text input)
- Last Name: Enter your Last Name (text input)
- Date of Birth: dd/mm/yyyy (date picker)
- Gender: Radio buttons for Male, Female, Others
- E-mail: Enter your Email (text input)
- Phone No: Enter your Phone No (text input)
- Address: Enter your Address (text area)
- Department: Enter your Department (text input)
- Skills: Enter your Skills (text input)
- Image: Choose file / No file chosen (file upload)
- Update Database (button)

CONNECTING EC2 TO OUR MAC

```
Downloads — ubuntu@ip-172-31-87-46: ~ — ssh -i mac-sam.pem ubuntu...
System load: 0.01          Processes: 101
Usage of /: 18.2% of 7.69GB Users logged in: 0
Memory usage: 21%        IPv4 address for eth0: 172.31.87.46
Swap usage: 0%

1 update can be applied immediately.
To see these additional updates run: apt list --upgradable

The list of available updates is more than a week old.
To check for new updates run: sudo apt update

The programs included with the Ubuntu system are free software;
the exact distribution terms for each program are described in the
individual files in /usr/share/doc/*/copyright.

Ubuntu comes with ABSOLUTELY NO WARRANTY, to the extent permitted by
applicable law.

To run a command as administrator (user "root"), use "sudo <command>".
See "man sudo_root" for details.

ubuntu@ip-172-31-87-46: $
```

INSTALLING MYSQL-CLIENT

```
Downloads — ubuntu@ip-172-31-87-46: ~ — ssh -i mac-sam.pem ubuntu...
Get:33 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu focal-security/main amd64 c-n-f Metadat
a [10.0 kB]
Get:34 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu focal-security/restricted amd64 Package
s [859 kB]
Get:35 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu focal-security/restricted Translation-e
n [122 kB]
Get:36 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu focal-security/restricted amd64 c-n-f M
etadata [532 B]
Get:37 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu focal-security/universe amd64 Packages
[698 kB]
Get:38 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu focal-security/universe Translation-en
[124 kB]
Get:39 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu focal-security/universe amd64 c-n-f Met
adata [14.3 kB]
Get:40 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu focal-security/multiverse amd64 Package
s [20.7 kB]
Get:41 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu focal-security/multiverse Translation-e
n [5196 B]
Get:42 http://security.ubuntu.com/ubuntu focal-security/multiverse amd64 c-n-f M
etadata [500 B]
Fetched 22.5 MB in 4s (5634 kB/s)
Reading package lists... Done
ubuntu@ip-172-31-87-46:~$ sudo apt-get install mysql-client
```

CONNECTING EC2 TO RDS

```
Downloads — ubuntu@ip-172-31-87-46: ~ — ssh -i mac-sam.pem ubuntu@ec2-44-...
ubuntu@ip-172-31-87-46:~$ mysql -h studentinfo.chws2t1slh2.us-east-1.rds.amazonaws.com -u
sam -p
Enter password:
Welcome to the MySQL monitor.  Commands end with ; or \g.
Your MySQL connection id is 22
Server version: 8.0.28 Source distribution

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owners.

Type 'help;' or '\h' for help. Type '\c' to clear the current input statement.

mysql>
```

Activate
Go to Set

CREATING TABLE IN MYSQL SHELL

```
mysql> use studentinfo;
Database changed
mysql> create table student(
-> stuid varchar(20),
-> fname varchar(20),
-> lname varchar(20),
-> dob date,
-> gender set('male','female','others'),
-> email varchar(40),
-> phoneno varchar(10),
-> address varchar(80),
-> dept varchar(20),
-> skill varchar(100));
Query OK, 0 rows affected (0.04 sec)

mysql> show tables;
+-----+
| Tables_in_studentinfo |
+-----+
| student                |
+-----+
1 row in set (0.01 sec)

mysql>
```

DEPLOYING THE WEBSITE TO AWS CLOUD

Website deployed in EC2 and information in RDS

CLONING THE WEBSITE CODE INTO EC2

```
ubuntu@ip-172-31-87-46:~$ git clone https://github.com/Samritha03/studentdatabase-aws.git
Cloning into 'studentdatabase-aws'...
Username for 'https://github.com': Samritha03
Password for 'https://Samritha03@github.com':
remote: Enumerating objects: 13, done.
remote: Counting objects: 100% (13/13), done.
remote: Compressing objects: 100% (10/10), done.
remote: Total 13 (delta 3), reused 13 (delta 3), pack-reused 0
Unpacking objects: 100% (13/13), 5.35 KiB | 1.78 MiB/s, done.
ubuntu@ip-172-31-87-46:~$ ls
studentdatabase-aws
ubuntu@ip-172-31-87-46:~$ cd studentdatabase-aws/
ubuntu@ip-172-31-87-46:~/studentdatabase-aws$
```

INFORMATION DEPLOYED IN RDS (MYSQL SHELL)

```
mysql> use studentinfo;
Database changed
mysql> show tables;
+-----+
| Tables_in_studentinfo |
+-----+
| student                |
+-----+
1 row in set (0.00 sec)

mysql> select * from student;
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| stuid | fname | lname | dob      | gender | email                               | dept | skill |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
| 39120101 | Samritha | Ravikumar | 2001-10-03 | female | samritha03102001@gmail.com        |      | Python |
| 9360471990 | 52, G.A.Road, Old Washermenpet, Chennai-21 |      |      |      |      |      |      |
+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+-----+
1 row in set (0.00 sec)

mysql>
```

IMAGE DEPLOYED IN S3

ensures that deployment is faster and more error-free, and it reduces costs. For example, AWS Cloud Formation automates the deployment of cloud environments. This helps to manage & maintain an organization's cloud infrastructure easily. There are many Cloud Computing courses for beginners and experts that cover automation for students, helping them understand in and out of the concept.

Increase in Mobile Analytics :

With increased mobile penetration worldwide, businesses understand that reaching customers through mobile channels is of utmost importance. AWS offers mobile analytics services that offer insights into user experience and engagement, giving businesses a way to improve their mobile platform.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

Amazon Web Services provides number of tools to simplify and automate the provisioning of infrastructure and deployment of applications. Each deployment service has a unique approach for managing application deployments and offers various strategies for updating your application. For best results, focus on your workload and choose a deployment service that is tailored to your specific needs As you plan, consider using deployment model approach, which uses a combination of deployment services for multiple applications throughout their lifecycle.

FUTURE WORK

More User-friendly Development Machine Learning:

With several new features and services constantly added to AWS, its offerings can sometimes be overwhelming. That struggle to navigate through its services will change in the future with AWS's focus on more user-friendly development. As such, AWS has added several features that simplify the development process, and adding to the AWS future scope.

Improved Compute Infrastructure :

Improved Compute infrastructure refers to the compute offerings of AWS such as Elastic Compute Cloud (EC2), Lambda, and more. With improved infrastructure, the Compute platform of AWS promises faster and more reliable services that improve user experience. Several of these improvements include more versatility and customization options for EC2 and offering server less options like AWS Lambda.

Higher Levels of Automation:

Increasing levels of automation in the cloud industry is inevitable. AWS continues to pursue this trend by automating more services and instances. Automation

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